

Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi A Well Known Scholar and Politician of Sindh

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ABSTRACT:

Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi is one of the Sindhis celebrated politician. He played a vital role in the movement of separation of Sindh from Bombay. He was a renowned worker of freedom movement of Pakistan. He belonged to the feudal family of Sindh. Pir Sahab achievement was not restricted only to the field of politics, nevertheless, he proved himself a great literary personality. This article sheds light on the political and literary achievements along with his services in the field of journalism. His literary works which were greatly appreciated is also given in this article. Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi (1905–1987) was a Pakistani politician, scholar, bureaucrat, journalist and well-known writer. He was from Rashdi Syed, those are calculated in Lakyari Syed's branch. He was the elder brother of scholar Pir Hassam-ud-Din Rashdi.

His father Pir Muhammad Hamid Shah lived at Bahman village, Ratodero Taluka, Larkana District, Sindh. Pir Shahab got his early education from Molvi Muhammad Soomar and Molvi Muhammad Sidiq. He taught himself Persian, Urdu, and English. He also studied English with Marmaduke Pickthall

Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi and Moulai Shedai were of the same age. Pir Sahib was a versatile and dynamic personality. He has met only a great journalist and competent politician. He was very close to Moulai Shedai. He belongs to Lakhiyaru Syed one of the ancestors Ali Maki migrated to Sindh in 1118 A.D. Ali Maki's posterity settled in Laki (Dau) and thus they were called Lakhiyari Syeds. Renowned saint Shah Sadruddin Alabyu Ranumat's lineage s as under: Syed Sadruddin Shah Mehmood bin Shah Hussain bin Shah Chakan in Syed Ali Maki. Syed Badauddin was the brother of Syed Sadruddin. Rashdi Syed جدامجد Syed Muhammad Rashid's genealogical lineage is as under which reackear to Syed Bahauddin.

Syed Muhammad Rashid bin Syed Muhammad Baqa bin Syed Muhammad Imam bin Syed Fateh Muhammad bin Syed Shukurallah bin Syed Othman bin Shah Khatan bin Shah Sanjar bin Shah Bolan bin Shah Hussain bin Syed Amir Ali bin Syed Bahaudin Alahye Rahmat. Syed Muhammad Rashid left this immortal domain on 1st Shaban, June 1818 A.D. Syed Muhammad Rashid was blessed with two sons; Syed Sibghatullah Shah, who was elected as Sahib-e-Durtan termed as Pir Pagaras. The second son named Syed Muhammad Yasin known as Sahib-a-Alam (Flag) or Jhanday Waro /main Sibghatullah Shah died on 18 February 1813 A.D.

Pir Mian Sibghatullah Shah also had two sons, Syed Ali Muhammad Shah was elder one and Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi if from this line of parentage. The other one was Syed Gohar Shah whose posterity is known as Pir Sahab of Pagaro. Syed Ali Muhammad Shah renowned in favor of his younger brother Syed Ali Muhammad Shah died on 17th July 1876. ⁽¹⁾

Syed Ali Muhammad Shah Rashidi was born on Friday, the 5th August 1905. He was sent to Madarsah at the age of three. Sindhi the mother tongue was not taught in schools, English ws not considered to study at all as they hated to work under English (Govt service). Persian was considered necessary. Pir Sahib started his education with Persian. Pir Sahib could not study Persian with full conversation as his teacher Mian Mihtab could not teach him well because of his personal problems.

Pir Sahib learned English in his village at Berhmanabad dero Larkana from two Hindu station masters Jeananad and Naraen. Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi could not get higher studies. In those days one Pir Sahib was staying with his grandfather, at a Memon;s House at Kemkies Sreet. There was a reading room beneath the building. Their Pir Sahib met a young men who told Pir Sahib that his name was Umardin from Talti district Dadu. He further told Pir Sahib that he had done his master and was a gold medalist. He told him that had come with Mian Abdul Rahim Shah of Sajawal and wanted to get a foreign scholarship for had doctorate. Pir Sahib told him that he was studying Persian from a Madarsah. Pir Sahib remarked that he was Pir and landlord and had no need to enter in govt. job, so he did not enter to get an advanced education. Umardin was surprised to hear all that and he advised Pir Sahib to avail the opportunity and get (acquire) higher education. ⁽²⁾.

Umardin convinced Pir Sahib's grandfather to send Pir Sahib in Colonel Brown's Cambridge School at Dorados. Pir Sahib went to the School but stayed there only one day.

Pir Sahib told his grandfather about that young man and asked him to help him get a scholarship.

Pir Sahib was a landlord and Piri too. He belonged to a system which was the feudal world around him was full of ignorance, leisure, luxury atrocities all the bad virtues. Landlords (feudal lords) had nothing to do, they wanted their time. In spite of all that Pir Sahib kept himself away from those evils. His contempt for such practices was only because of his mother's brought up who told him that times were going to change and feudalism and spirit were soon to perish. All he could give was by his hard work and education and strive to achieve something. (3) Pir Sahib did not go to any college, but due to his own efforts, he not only learned Sindhi and Urdu but also got command on the English language.

Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi was a dynamite and versatile personality, he achieved a lot of success through hard work there is an analysis of his practical endeavor and important values.

Pir Sahib's major accomplishments are in three fields, Journalism- his literary works and his political career. He revolted against the feudal trends and started his career as a journalist. At the age of 15 he developed interest in writing articles for newspapers, Thus in 1924, he joined Sindhi Newspaper as نامہ نگار and thus started his career as a journalist inspired by Moulana Abul Kalam Azad's newspaper Al-Hilal الهلال he initiated a monthly newspaper "Al-Rashdi" الراشدی which were printed in Sukkur but was issued from the village. (4)

In 1940, he issued first English newspaper named "Muslim Voice" which printed till 1946. At first, the newspaper was issued from Sukkur and then from Karachi In 1946, Sindhi's Progressive Muslim under the leadership of G.M. Sayed came into conflict with Muhammad Ali Jinnah's Muslim League. To activate their motives on magazine or newspaper named Qurbani as started and Pir Sahib appointed editor of the newspaper. Except writing editorials he started writing on politics and affirm Qurbani as stopped in 1948. From 1949 to 1959 he remained editor of the newspaper issued from Karachi named "Sindh Observer". During then particular period he In literary contents it Dawn News editor Altaf Hussain on literary grounds, which is a significant basic chapter of Pakistan Journalism's History. After the establishment of Pakistan, his literary works earned him a high esteem and status in journalism. Due to which from 1950 to 1952 he was chosen as the President of All Pakistan Editor's Association named as Newspaper Editors Conference. The president of Newspaper Editors Conference, he was appointed the head of the delegates of a journalist who visited India, Egypt and United Kingdom. In 1951 he was chosen unanimously President of Journalist Press Commission, which was made to promote Pak-Bharat friendship. Last of his work as a journalist was a weekly newspaper named Eastern Express from 1954 to 1955. Thus he ended his career as a journalist but he his thrust and for literature and journalism through articles writing which he wrote at different times. He wrote column in Urdu newspaper "Jang" entitled as Maktoub-e-Mashriq In the same newspaper, he started a new series of a column named Mashriq-o-Maghrib and the other is Waghaira Waghiara. During the same period, he wrote a column named Ran and Pandh in Sindhi newspaper "Ibrat" published from Hyderabad. In the column, he provided valuable information about Hosh Muhammad Sheedi's (Shaheed-e-Sindh) grievances doctrine. In 1971, he wrote a column in English named "A Point of View" in Daily Jang's edition published from London. In the year 1975 he started writing columns series entitled as Impression and Reflection. Throughout his career as a journalist, Pir Sahib not only promoted a political point of view but he gave novelty ظرافت in the field of journalism(s).

Pir Sahib's every aspect of life is worth mentioning and قابل رشک but we find no match of his in the field of column writing not only in Sindhi but in Urdu and English. Columns written by Pir Sahib are precious embellished with priceless pleasures in the field of politics, sociology, literary and literature.

He portrayed his ideas in such a marvelous manner that it was impossible for the readers not to get impressed by them.

He served as Pakistan's ambassador to the Philippines from 1957 to 1961 and was Doyen of the diplomatic corps there. He also served as ambassador to China for 10 months, during which he concluded negotiations for the border agreement between Pakistan and China that later on, Zulfikar Ali Bhutto signed on behalf of Pakistan. He went Hong Kong for trade and journalism.

Rashdi wrote books in Sindhi, Urdu, and English on politics, biographies, local issues and diaries

Keywords: Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi, Politician of Sindh

PIR ALI MUHAMMAD RASHDI'S POLITICAL ACHIEVEMENTS:

Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi rendered voluminous services in the field of politics. He started his political career from his native village. He then associated himself with Khan Bahadur Muhammad Ayub Khoro. He used to provide Khoro Sahib historical evidence and literature for his written contents.

Shaikh Abdul Majeed was the person who initiated the idea of separation of Sindh from Bombay in 1919. Prior to that a delegate of Sindhi's patriotic leaders met with Sir Montague and asked for the separation of Sindh from Bombay. In 1919 Provincial Political Committee of Congress (after a research) presented a report and pleaded for separation of Sindh famous Hindu politician passed a resolution for separation of Sindh from Bombay.

The resolution was seconded by Muslim League All Pakistan Conference and other political parties. In the 42nd session of All India Congress, it has resolved that Sindh should be separated from Bombay and given the status of a province. In 1928 Sindhi's Muslim Hindus and passes jointly established Sindh Azad Conference, to start the struggle for the revival of Sindh's status. (6)

Pir Sahib founded a party named Anjuman Senate Rshdiya. He contested in the election through his members and issued newspaper named Ali Rashid to promote and publicize his members. He took an active part in organizing a Sindh Azad Conference under the president ship of Allama Abdullah Yousuf Ali. In the Conference Hindu, the community was assured to get their rights. Resolutions passed in the Conference ere sent to Secretary of State and to the President of British government working committee of Sindh Azad Conference consisted of Sir Shahnawaz Bhatti as President, Ayub Khoro as Vice President and Miran Muhammad Shah as appointed General Secretary. A session of Sindh Hindu Conference was organized on 26th January 1933, in which Hindus vigorous opposed the separation of Sindh from Bombay, they also established an office in London for this purpose.

Sir Agha Khan and Dr. Shifat Ahmed to appear the Muslims. Dr. Gur Bakhsh warned British government that if Sindh's separation was not granted, Sindhis, Balochis and Pathan community attack sub-continent. Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi replied to the opposition through the newspaper Sitara-e-Sindh Sindh's especial customs. (7)

The role played by these newspapers published from Sukkur is truly memorable.

Rashdi started his political career in 1926 by joining the Sindh Muhammadan Association. He also struggled for the eviction Sindh from Bombay. He joined the Peoples Party of Sir Shahnawaz Bhutto in 1934. He was also considered among the founders of Sindh It had Party. He joined the Muslim League in 1938 and supported the foundation of Pakistan as Secretary of the Sindh Provincial Muslim League and as Secretary of the Foreign Committee of the All India Muslim League. According to the late Yusuf Abdullah Haroon (elder statesman of Pakistan), Rashdi was involved in the drafting of the Pakistan Resolution of 1940 that is also known as the Lahore Resolution. After 1947 he was instrumental in the reinstatement of the Gaddi of Pir Pagara and ignored the Frontier Regulation. He won the seat of MPA in the Sindh Assembly in the election of 1953 and was appointed as Minister of Revenue. In the era of Mohammad Ayub Khuhro, he served as Minister of Health, Revenue, and Information. He also served as Federal Minister for Information under Prime Minister Chaudhry Muhammad Ali and resigned in 1957.

Pir Sahib realized that he could achieve political benefits for his people through association with influential personalities. He, therefore, affiliated himself with Larkana as influential personality Muhammad Ayub Khoro. Benefited by him he remains members of Local Board of Larkana From 1933 to 1936. He also remained members of a school establishment by the Local Board. He rendered his best to mean Sindh Azad Party in 1934. In 1936 when Sindh was separated from Bombay he played a vital role to establish Sindh It had Party. He resourcefully helped out All India Muslim League to enter into Sindh Assembly. For that, he highlighted the personality of Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah in Sindh. After that, he associated himself with the cause of All India Muslim League. He devoted himself to popularize Muslim League and to it by giving exposure to Muslim League's Ministers and Members among the nevertheless he served Muslim League in Punjab in the capacity of Secretary to Naab Shahnaz Khan Madoot (8) Association with politics looked till 1970 and meanwhile, he served as foreign delegates from China and Philippine. We notice major difference in his political point of view before and

after partition. Before partition his political approach was nationalistic and revolutionary, after the partitions he became a yes man who was contented with virtuous mainstream versatility of his political approach. He witnessed after partitions nevertheless he remained very active in the struggle to make Karachi under of Sindh. We also writing his negative approach where he favored and worked for the establishment of one unit. We can justify it as a human nature but he was a virtuous and wise person, like which are rarely found with the history of Sindh. Pir Sahib was an egoist and خوددار worker. Once G.M. Sayed happened to visit Clifton, he found Pir Sahib and Sir Abdullah Haroon seated on Haji Sahib remarked saying: Syed Sahib I know him (Rashdi Sahib) very well, he is great. Whether he would entrance more he ill leads me to the jail. Shah Sahib in spite of same flaws, Rashdi isthose rare people who are so blessed. After Haji Abdullah Haroon's death, he being unsatisfied with Muslim League high command and local leadership became He mostly stayed out of Sindh. After the election of 1945, a collective govt. was framed with Congress. To make the masses reconciliation he promoted his point of view through Qurban. He also published phosphatethe matter. Assembly could not last longer. New elections were held under the orders of Governor. G.M. Sayed made election petition, Pir Sahib remained with Syed Sahib in his struggle. After the establishment of Pakistan, Pir Sahib rejoined Muslim League. He was elected as a member of Sindh Assembly from the platform of Muslim League through the elections held in 1953. Prior to this when Governor Deen Muhammad was running the government of Sindh through Pir Sahib he got three major tasks done from him:

1. Restarted saint of Pir Pagara
2. Dismissed frontier regulation
3. Dismissed of Colonel Tribes Act and exemptions of Hurr from confirmation appearance/attendance in the court.

HIS PUBLICATIONS:

The following are some selected publications:

1. ***Suffering from Sindh***: this book is a historical document about Sindh's separation from Bombay, this document was published with the name of *Ayub Khoro*. Who was the leader of the movement? Pir Sahib worked as his society. Nevertheless, its Sindhi translation is done by Pir Ali Muhammad Rashdi. It was published in 1930.
2. ***Hayat-e-Masoom***: This pamphlet was about Mir Masoom Shah Bukhari. It was published in 1932.
3. ***Faryad-e-Sindh***: this booklet consists articles which advocate the Muslim League's motto to exhibit Pakistan and more aware people of Sindh about the misfortune of they opposed the e making of Pakistan.
4. ***Current Political Affairs***: this booklet also included articles from Qurbani the newspaper. In the above-mentioned booklet, Pir Sahib has to revise predicted about Muslim League' politics Pakistan and Sindh's future. It was published in 1940.
5. ***Sindh Jee Inqalabi Tehreek***:
6. ***Sindh Ways and Days***: The reader is given a lucid and colorful picture of the favorite pastime of Sindh: Shikar. It is an introduction to the country's renowned marksmen, the manner of hunting, and weapons used, interspersed with adventures encountered in all its expert detail, and its importance in the socio-political fabric of the subcontinent.

- *Uhee Denhin Uhee Shenih* (3 volumes)
- *Jager Dari Jo Khatimo*
- *Sindh jee Nain Wizarat*
- *Boodin Ja Imdadi Masla*
- *Cheen jee* (diary)
- *Imam Inqlaab*

CONCLUSION:

The family tree of Syed Ali Muhammad Rashdi is traced with Lakhyari Syeds. He belonged to a feudal family. His works are extended in three main institutions i.e. Journalism, Literature, and Politics.

He issued 1s newspaper in 1940 and wrote columns for different newspapers till 1974 in Sindhi, Urdu and English languages. The writer has analyzed this period of his life.